

VII International Forum on Teacher Education

Practical Aspects of Teaching Migrant Children in Primary School

Lera A. Kamalova* (a), Galina P. Zhirkova (b), Narine S. Putulyan (c)

(a), (c) Kazan Federal University, 420008, Kazan (Russia), 18 Kremlyovskaya street, leraax57@mail.ru;
(b) ITMO University, 197101, St. Petersburg (Russia), 49 Kronverksky Pr., bldg. A

Abstract

The problem of adaptation of children and teenagers from migrant families to the educational system is becoming urgent. The educational system is the key institution of socio-cultural and socio-psychological adaptation. Scientists write about the need to develop special measures, educational programs aimed at integrating migrant children into a new socio-cultural environment, and organizing comprehensive educational work with migrant children. It is also pointed out that the teaching and learning process of migrant children should include the study of the personality of a migrant student as a socio-pedagogical phenomenon, to the justification of the specifics of the goals, content and methods of educational work with migrant children in a foreign cultural educational environment. They point to the development of a special program for their education and upbringing, the identification of features of adaptation, cultural identification and self-realization in various socio-cultural conditions. The purpose of the study is to test the effectiveness of the authors' program of teaching migrant children in primary school. Quantitative research methods and an anonymous survey were conducted. An education program for teaching and socialization of migrant children in primary school was created. Methodological recommendations on the use of modern technologies and the practice of educational activities of primary school teachers with migrant children were developed. The results of the study can be used in the educational process of Russian and foreign educational institutions, in the practice of primary school teachers.

Keywords: migrants, primary school, educational work, activity, adaptation, socialization.

© 2021 Lera A. Kamalova, Galina P. Zhirkova, Narine S. Putulyan

This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published by Kazan federal university and peer-reviewed under responsibility of IFTE-2021 (VII International Forum on Teacher Education)

* Corresponding author. E-mail: leraax57@mail.ru

Introduction

The problems of interethnic and intercultural interaction are currently a relevant subject of research in science and practice. In recent decades, migration has become one of the world's most important problems.

Migration processes around the world, including Russia, have reached unprecedented proportions. In the migration flow to the Russian Federation, children and adolescents make up more than a quarter of all incoming migrants. Migration processes lead to the emergence of a whole complex of "children's" problems, which are characterized by certain specifics and which require their detailed and urgent solution.

The most important problems are psychological stresses associated with a forced change of residence (adolescents, due to their dependence on adults, are always forced migrants) and a violation of the structure of the usual cultural and communicative, kinship-family, natural-territorial and other ties, identity crisis, mismatch in the system of values and social norms, general dissatisfaction with various aspects of life and with oneself, adaptation of arriving children and adolescents to the requirements of the Russian system of secondary, secondary special or higher education, lack of the necessary conditions and quality of education. Also difficulties in getting used to a new communication environment for a child, and as a result, not infrequently occurring states of alienation and rejection, anxiety and mental tension, aggression and increased conflict, etc. The question of the need to develop specialized measures aimed at integrating migrants into the new socio-cultural environment is increasingly being raised.

The works of Russian scientists develop the theoretical foundations of multicultural education and substantiate the premise that the historical diversity of national and ethnic cultures creates positive conditions for the development of multicultural education and pedagogical support for migrant children in a multicultural society: Bondarevskaya (1999), Dmitriev (1999), Makaev, Malkova and Suprunova (1999) and Palatkina (2001). Scientists develop the contents and give justification of the interpretations of such concepts as "educational support" and "protection" of migrant children in multicultural education.

Socio-pedagogical and psychological work with children of labor migrants is reflected in the works of Levchenko, Trubavina and Tsushko (2008). According to Dmitriev (1999), multicultural education is a way to resist racism, prejudice, xenophobia, bias, ethnocentrism, and hatred based on cultural differences.

According to Makaev, Malkova and Suprunova (1999), multicultural education is the formation of a person capable of active and effective life in a multinational and multicultural environment, who has a developed sense of understanding and respect for other cultures.

Pedagogical support must necessarily include special measures related to the development and maintenance of pedagogical conditions for migrant children experiencing certain difficulties. Scientists emphasize that when organizing this process, the teacher must take into account the uniqueness and identity of the student and support them through self-affirmation in the culture. The teacher must design pedagogical interaction taking into account the personal capabilities and characteristics of the teacher and the student based on the "subjective experience" of the latter; to rely on a personal approach in multicultural education (Jalalova, 2009).

Russian researchers believe that the specifics of multicultural education methods are determined by the dialogical nature of the functioning and development of culture, the level of ethnocultural identification of the student, the level of knowledge of students about the multicultural environment. They are determined by their emotional and behavioral culture, which requires the use of active methods: dialogue, conversation, discussion, modeling, design, reconstruction, role-playing games, reflexive methods (Palatkina, 2001).

Hence, one of the main tasks of the educational environment of a modern school is to assist the student in establishing a culture of human relationships and forming a person with a highly responsible position. The development of a respectful relationship between students of different nationalities, a tolerant attitude towards representatives of other cultures and traditions, and building of a friendly environment in the classroom and school are the main tasks of the teaching staff of each school where migrant children study.

The presence of a real connection between the family and the educational institution in a multicultural educational space is an important condition for the integration of a migrant into a multicultural environment. Recently, the role of parents in the educational process has significantly increased. In addition to regular visits to the educational institution where the child is studying, they are charged with preparing children for education in this educational institution, as well as actively participating in educational activities. Often, the difficult living conditions of migrants do not allow parents to participate properly in the educational process of their children. The main inhibiting factors are ignorance of the Russian language, lack of free time from work, and their own illiteracy.

However, nowadays, the problem of organizing the educational process with migrant children, taking into account the specifics of educational activities with migrant children in primary school, assisting migrant students in the process of their adaptation, cultural identification and self-realization in a foreign cultural environment remains underdeveloped in pedagogical theory.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is to test the effectiveness of the author's program of teaching migrant children in primary school:

1. create an author's program for teaching migrant children in primary school;
2. to prove the effectiveness of the author's program of teaching migrant children in primary school based on a dialogue of cultures, providing social adaptation, cultural identification and creating conditions for self-realization of migrant children in a foreign cultural environment;
3. to develop methodological recommendations for teaching migrant children in primary school.

Literature review

The works of Russian scientists substantiate the main provisions of multicultural education. The process of entry of migrant students into a new culture is described in the literature by the terms "adaptation", "integration", "acculturation", "culture shock". Today, the key term describing the desired result in a migration situation is integration. The result of cultural integration (or acculturation) is the psychological and socio-cultural adaptation of migrant children. Psychological adaptation includes a set of internal psychological consequences of the experience when entering a new cultural environment (Khukhlaev, 2005).

Chudnovsky (2006) recommends using a set of methods and techniques in the process of diagnostic examination of children of migrant workers. In particular, monitoring the child's behavior and recording the results obtained using the technique. Observations are used to study the manifestations of depressive states, social maladjustment in schoolchildren from migrant families. The scientist draws attention to the following signs: the frequency of mood changes, the presence of somatic diseases, impaired appetite, sleep disorders, sudden changes in the child's physical activity and others.

According to Samoukina (1997), the tasks of social and pedagogical work with children from migrant families are determined by the problems and needs of children, the solution to which requires both the integration of educational influences on the child in a general educational institution, and keeping records of the children whose parents are abroad, as well as mandatory communication with the child, through conversations or counseling, the development of an objective self-assessment of children, life plans, and career guidance.

An important fact is that in children education, the example of parents is of particular importance, which is learned through imitation of behavior. In migrant families, children do not have the necessary example of parents, since one or both of them are working abroad. We consider it appropriate to add that such an important part of family education as communication with parents and joint leisure activities in migrant families are limited or impossible, which is caused by the peculiarities of the life of this category of families (Samoukina, 1997).

It is determined that the problems of children from migrant families are mainly psychological in nature. This is due to a number of features of their personality. For example, some of them are characterized by isolation; these children have a sense of guilt towards their parents. They consider themselves guilty that their parents went abroad. On the other hand, other representatives of this group tend to be demonstrative and attention-seeking (Samoukina, 1997).

As Katolik notes (2016), children from migrant families have problems in the emotional and motivational sphere at the stage of primary socialization, which affects communication, study and future work.

The decline of school performance and parental authority lead to social and pedagogical neglect, sometimes with a delay in mental development. Such a child falls out of the influence of family and school. They have low self-esteem, a feeling of emotional insecurity and uselessness; there is a distortion of value orientations and moral concepts. Such a child has trouble in a stressful situation and is not able to speak out their experiences; they have lost their vital support and an unformed idea of the meaning of life (Katolik, 2016).

Molchanov (2019) points out that almost all children from migrant families have a shared feature – a violation of socialization, which manifests itself in different ways: inability to adapt to an unfamiliar environment, to new circumstances, violations of sexual orientation, loss or absence of value orientations, ethics, lack of spirituality, loss of interest in knowledge, bad habits, cruelty, aggressiveness, laziness. Children from migrant families are quite independent, but they are not inclined to lead and do not like to take responsibility for others. Special pedagogical and psychological approaches are required because these children are emotionally vulnerable (ibid.).

Since children from migrant families do not have the opportunity to communicate with their parents, their socialization takes place outside the family, under the influence of various factors. The Internet has the greatest influence on the development of the personality of children whose parents work away from home (Molchanov, 2019). Thus, there is a situation in which the family loses the function of the main agent of socialization of the child of a migrant worker, and the real social environment of its social upbringing is replaced by a "virtual space".

Based on the above, we can conclude that there is a social need to organize purposeful educational work in primary schools to form a multicultural personality that combines systemic knowledge in the field of ethnoculture, harmonious national identity, intellectual values orientation, tolerance and the readiness for the interethnic dialogue. Such educational work is aimed at mastering universal values, introducing people to the culture of other peoples, preserving centuries-old traditions, creating the necessary conditions for their further development, and educating migrant children based on tolerance (Palatkina, 2001).

Foreign scientists study the problem of multiculturalism, multicultural education and upbringing of students, conditions of education, language and socio-cultural adaptation of migrant students. The works of foreign scientists Berry (1997), Banks (1996) and Makarova and Birman (2016) substantiate the premise that the historically established diversity of national and ethnic cultures creates positive conditions for the development of multicultural education.

Banks (1996) studied tolerance as a social and professional value, which is an important and integral element of the social competencies of a modern person.

Foreign researchers note that children in the new conditions of living and learning experience a culture shock. Scientists distinguish such aspects of culture shock as 1. the tension that accompanies the efforts necessary for psychological adaptation (leads to fatigue). 2. A sense of loss or deprivation (status, friends, homeland, profession, property). 3. A sense of rejection (the new culture rejects the migrant, and he rejects the new culture). 4. Failure in the role structure (roles and expectations), confusion in self-identification, values, feelings. 5. A feeling of anxiety based on various emotions (surprise, disgust, indignation, resentment) that arise as a result of awareness of cultural differences. 6. The feeling of powerlessness, inferiority because of the awareness of the inability to cope with a new situation (Berry, 1997).

Makarova and Birman (2016) concludes that migrant students go through a difficult path of adaptation in the receiving country. For the assimilation of a migrant child into a foreign cultural environment, it is necessary to preserve the ethnic component of the multicultural educational space, that is, to preserve and transfer the self-identity of the national community.

Switala and Gurba (2019) study the problems associated with the inclusion of migrant and refugee children in the Polish education system and providing them with conditions for proper development. The main thing in the school environment is the education of respect for migrant children, which contributes to multicultural integration. This process is complex, given the existing stereotypes and other factors that lead to prejudice and fear of strangers.

Lemay (2018) explores the issue of cultural politics related to the influence of religion on the lives of Filipino migrants living in Japan. With the arrival of migrant children in primary school, the influence of Filipino mothers on their children decreases and parents spend less time with their children.

Scientists pay attention to the issue of parental participation in the educational activities of the school with migrant children. Foreign scientists concluded that the degree of involvement of parents in the educational process of migrants depends on the environmental conditions (economic factor, the level of education, participation in social activities) and emotional and motivational conditions. The emotional-motivational sphere is the parents' perception of the educational process as a way of socio-economic success. Emotional support for parents consists in talking to children about the importance of education. Thus, parents are able to contribute to the area of the child's life in which the teacher is powerless.

The researchers, Herwartz-Emden and Kuffner (2006), studied two aspects of the personality of migrant children: self-concept and self-esteem, and their possible impact on the school performance of migrant children. Success in school and the educational activities of migrant children is closely related to the process of acculturation, entry into the foreign cultural environment of the host society.

Sun, Chui, Chen and Fu (2020) studied the patterns of adaptation of migrant children from rural areas in China compared to their peers in urban schools. Public school attendance can help children adapt, including access to more family resources and social relationships, the gap in adaptation between migrant children from public and migrant schools raises concerns about the upward mobility of migrant children from dysfunctional families, which requires greater attention and support from local authorities.

Cheung Judge analyzes the problem of raising migrant children whose parents live abroad separately from their children. Schools where migrants study, often teach many children whose parents live abroad and decide to "leave" or "send" their children to be sent "home". However, little attention is paid to how transnational parenting is carried out by non-related subjects in educational institutions.

Guo and colleagues (2021) investigated the importance of developing reading skills by the end of the third grade for the further academic performance of migrant children. The researchers evaluated the impact of providing self-selected, development-appropriate books on the reading performance and summer reading rate of students in migrant schools in China, using randomized controlled research. The intervention program improved word reading scores in the second graders and the number of summer readings. This has been particularly useful for children with low academic achievement and children from disadvantaged families.

The results have implications for improving the academic performance of migrant children in migrant schools in China and similar developing countries, especially where parental support cannot be expected for the academic development of children.

Methodology

In the course of the study a set of various methods were used: theoretical methods (analysis of the works of teachers and psychologists on the research problem; analysis of methodological and educational literature; theoretical analysis of the main provisions of the proposed methodology; theoretical justification of the research problem); empirical methods (observation, stating and forming a pedagogical experiment, questionnaires, testing, conversations, and analysis of the results of experimental work).

The experimental base of the study was two schools of Zelenodolsk Municipal district of the Republic of Tatarstan: "Grammar school No. 16" and "Grammar school No. 5 with the Tatar ethnonational component". The experiment took place in the 2020/21 academic year. The experimental work involved the following participants:

- 1) Experimental group (EG) (27 people, including 14 migrants): students of the 3rd grade of "Grammar school No. 5 with the Tatar ethnonational component" of Zelenodolsk Municipal district of the Republic of Tatarstan;
- 2) Control group (CG) (27 people, including 13 migrants): students of the 3rd grade of "Grammar school No. 16" of the Zelenodolsk Municipal district of the Republic of Tatarstan.

The experiment was conducted in three stages: ascertaining (September 2020), forming (September 2020 – March 2021), control (March 2021).

The ascertaining stage involved the development of psychological, pedagogical and organizational conditions for the organization of educational activities with children in primary school.

At the first stage, an experimental platform was created, the process of training and upbringing of migrant children was monitored during various educational activities, and the research topic was tested at the initial stage of the ascertaining experiment.

The forming stage is aimed at substantiating the conditions for organizing the educational process that helps migrant students in the process of their adaptation, cultural identification and self-realization in a foreign cultural environment.

At this stage, the concept of the study was clarified and adjusted, and a training experiment among primary school students was conducted.

The analysis, generalization and systematization of the obtained data and the design of the study were carried out.

Quantitative research methods were used: an anonymous survey of 54 students of the 3rd grades of «Grammar school No. 16" and "Grammar school No. 5" of Zelenodolsk, the Republic of Tatarstan.

Results

In the course of the research "Diagnosis of the level of social isolation of the individual" (Russell & Fergusson, 2012), "Diagnostics of the education of students of 1-4 grades" (Kapustin, 2001); Test "Level of cooperation in children's groups" test were used (Kapustin, 2001).

Figure 1. Rapid diagnosis of the level of social isolation of the individual (experimental and control group).

"Diagnosis of the level of social isolation of the individual" (Russell & Fergusson, 2012).

In the experimental and control groups, a high degree of isolation in both groups-(55% and 52%) is shown, an average degree-36% and 40%, and a low degree-8% and 8%.

At the stage of the ascertaining experiment, the "Diagnosis of the upbringing of students in grades 1-4" (Kapustin, 2001) was carried out. Criteria for the level of education: from 0 to 30 % - low level, from 31 to 60% - medium level; from 61 to 100% - high level.

Table 1. The level of education of students (experimental and control groups)

№	Criteria of education	Total number of points of the class		% of the total number of points	
		EG	CG	EG	CG
1.	Curiosity	135	108	50%	40%
2.	Attitude to school	108	108	40%	40%
3.	Attitude to work	108	108	40%	40%
4.	Attitude to nature	108	108	40%	40%
5.	Aesthetic taste	81	81	30%	30%
6.	Attitude to yourself	108	108	40%	40%
7.	Total: number of points	648 points	621 points	40%	38,2%

The diagnostic results showed the level of education of students in the experimental and control groups: 40% and 38.2% - this is the average level of education of students.

At the stage of the ascertaining experiment, the diagnosis "The level of cooperation in the children's team" was carried out (Kapustin, 2001).

Table 2. The level of cooperation in the children's team (experimental and control groups)

	Experimental group	Control group
The value of the school	0,5	0,5
The value of the class	0,5	0,5
The value of the of the person	0,5	0,5
The value of the creativity	0,5	0,5
The value of the dialogue	1,00	1,00
The value of the reflection	0,5	0,5
The value of teacher's creativity	1,00	1,00
The value of the teacher's dialogicity	0,5	0,5
The value of the teacher's reflection	0,5	0,5
The value of the teacher's frankness	0,5	0,5

The diagnostic results show a low level of children cooperation both in control and experimental groups: 55%.

Diagnostics according to the method of Kapustin (2001) found that in the experimental and control groups, students want to contact, communicate, create (the value of creativity is 1,00 and 1,00), but they do not know how to do it, they are not taught the ways of communication and collaborative activity. At the same time, students of both groups highly appreciate the role of the teacher in teaching students to cooperate (creativity of the teacher - 1,00 and 1,00).

At the stage of the formative experiment, the following goals were set: 1. to create organizational and pedagogical conditions for educational work with migrant children; 2. to form the upbringing of migrant children; 3. to develop the personal qualities of migrant students; 4. to form the skills of cooperation in the classroom.

During the formative experiment during the 2020-2021 academic year in the experimental class, we used various educational activities conducted in the context of a dialogue of cultures: games, quizzes, festivals, contests, competitions, concerts, projects, performances. We have held multinational festivals, exhibitions, presentations of national costumes, cuisine, crafts, folklore and theatre events, including festivals of family theatres and folklore groups. These events serve to preserve and develop the traditions of multinational communication.

- A program for the education and socialization of migrant children in grades 1-4 of primary school was created. The author's program of educational work with migrant children in primary school is based on the following principles:
- Reflection in the educational material of humanistic ideas, ideas of freedom and non-violence;
- Characteristics of unique ethnic, original national features in the cultures of the peoples of the world;
- Discovering in the cultures of different peoples the common elements of traditions that allow to live in peace, tolerance and harmony;
- Introducing students to world culture, revealing the process of globalization, the interdependence of countries and peoples in modern conditions;
- Humanism, which expresses unconditional faith in the good principles inherent in the child;
- Democracy, based on the recognition of equal rights and obligations of adults and children, providing the latter with freedom of life in the family, social environment;
- Tolerance, tolerance for different views, mores, habits, to the peculiarities of different peoples;
- Competence, i.e. the need for the formation of special abilities of teachers and students to master

the knowledge of the education of an intellectual personality;

- The basic basis of the content of multicultural education, which is intended to act as a value-cultural, personality-oriented approach.

Recommendations for organizing educational activities in primary schools with migrant children were developed:

- full inclusion of migrant students in the socio-cultural environment of the school;
- adaptation of the socio-cultural environment of the school to migrants;
- creation of conditions for intercultural communication at school;
- promotion of the positive influence of migrant students on the development of the school;
- cooperation with parents of migrant children;
- development of communication skills;
- formation of confident behavior and social success;
- development of the ability to make moral choices.

The program of educational work with migrant children in primary schools is aimed at integrating migrant children into society through education; ensuring the relationship of social, cultural and linguistic adaptation, ensuring bilingualism and biculturalism in the education of migrant children; creating conditions for migrant students to preserve their own language, intellectual and emotional contacts with their native culture; taking into account the "threshold of mentality" when touching different cultures.

The program includes educational activities in 5 main blocks: language, basic knowledge, emotional state, social skills, cultural norms and rules.

Educational activities were conducted with migrant students of the experimental group:

- The Language block (educational games "My language is my friend", "Language is the soul of the people" and others);
- The Basic Knowledge block: (quizzes "Do you know mathematics?," "What? Where? When?" and others);
- Emotional state block: (trainings "Me and my class", "Me and my family", "My well-being at school" and others);
- Social skills block (team building games "I'm in the class", "My friend" and others);
- Cultural norms and rules block ("How to behave in school", "How to behave in public places", "How to behave with strangers" and others).

At the stage of the control experiment, the goals were set: to check the level of education of migrant students, the level of adaptation of migrant children in the new socio-cultural environment, the level of cooperation of children in the classroom.

Experimental work was carried out with younger students in the experimental and control groups. At the stage of the control experiment, the diagnostics "Diagnostics of the level of social isolation of the individual" (Russel & Fergusson, 2012); "Diagnostics of the upbringing of students in grades 3-5" (Kapustin, 2001); the test "The level of cooperation in the children's team" (Kapustin, 2001) were carried out.

At the stage of the control experiment, the "Diagnosis of the level of social isolation of the individual" was carried out (Russell & Fergusson, 2012).

Figure 2. Rapid diagnosis of the level of social isolation of the individual in the experimental and control groups

The results of the rapid diagnostics of the level of social isolation of the individual in the experimental and control groups showed a high degree of isolation – 7.7 and 70%, an average degree - 2.6% and 1.1%, and a low degree - 67% and 18%, respectively.

Thus, the diagnosis showed a positive dynamics of changes in the experimental group: the number of migrant children with a low degree of isolation of personality increased from 8% to 67%, with an average degree of isolation decreased from 36% to 2.6%, with a high degree of isolation decreased from 55% to 7.7%. In the control group, there were minor changes: a high degree of isolation-from 52% to 79% of the personality, an average degree of isolation of the personality - from 40% to 1.1%, a low degree of isolation of the personality-from 8% to 18%.

Table 3. The level of education of students (Kapustin, 2001) (experimental and control group)

№	Criteria of education	Total number of points of the class		% of the total number of points	
		EG	CG	EG	CG
1.	Curiosity	216	135	80%	50%
2.	Attitude to school	189	135	70%	50%
3.	Attitude to work	189	135	70%	50%
4.	Attitude to nature	162	135	60%	50%
5.	Aesthetic taste	189	108	70%	40%
6.	Attitude to yourself	216	135	80%	50%
7.	Total: number of points	1171 points	783 points	71%	38,3%

The results of the diagnosis of the level of education showed that in the experimental group there were significant changes in the education of migrant children: from 40% to 71% indicates a high level of education. In the control group, there were minor changes: from 38.2 % to 38.3% - this is the average level of education of students.

Table 4. The level of cooperation in the children's team (the method of Kapustin) (experimental group)

	Experimental group	Control group
The value of the school	1,00	0,5
The value of the class	1,00	0,5
The value of the of the person	1,00	0,5
The value of the creativity	1,00	0,5
The value of the dialogue	1,00	1,00
The value of the reflection	1,00	0,5
The value of teacher's creativity	1,00	1,00

The value of the teacher's dialogicity	0,5	0,5
The value of the teacher's reflection	1,00	0,5
The value of the teacher's frankness	0,5	0,5

The diagnostic results show a high level of cooperation of children in the experimental group (75%) and a low level in the control group (55%).

Discussions

A program for teaching and socialization of migrant children in grades 1-4 of primary school was developed. The program of educational work with migrant children in primary school is based on 9 following principles: humanistic ideas, ideas of freedom and non-violence; original national features in the cultures of the peoples of the world; discovering the common elements of the traditions of the peoples of the world; introducing the students to world culture; humanism; democracy; tolerance; competence; multicultural education. Recommendations for organizing educational activities in primary schools with migrant children were developed.

The theoretical and practical contribution of the study is:

- The organizational and pedagogical conditions for the organization of the educational process for migrant children in primary school are investigated;
- It is shown that the practical aspects of teaching migrant children creates conditions for the formation of the personality of a student who is ready for creativity in a modern multicultural and multinational environment, who preserves their socio-cultural identity and respect other cultural and ethnic communities, races and beliefs.
- It is demonstrated that the system of educational activities with migrant children in primary school in the context of a dialogue of cultures helps migrant students in the process of their adaptation, cultural identification and self-realization in a foreign cultural environment;
- Methodological recommendations for the organization of educational activities with migrant children in primary school in the context of a dialogue of cultures have been developed.

Conclusion

The study showed a direct relationship between the conditions of the organization of the educational process in primary schools where migrant children study, and the level of their cultural identification, upbringing, cooperation with each other and self-realization in a foreign cultural environment and the success of migrant students. The study confirmed the assumption that the specifics of educational activities with migrant children are associated with five different groups of characteristics: language, basic knowledge, emotional state, social skills, and cultural norms and rules.

The system of educational work with migrant children has shown the need to take into account the specifics of educational work in primary schools: an educational environment based on a dialogue of cultures that promotes the introduction of migrant children to the culture and traditions of different peoples, the preservation of their national culture, self-consciousness, as well as the establishment of contacts with a new society, the ability to navigate in the new, rapidly changing circumstances of the host society; learning the Russian language based on a communicative approach; conducting joint activities of migrant children with their parents; systematic participation of migrant students in social and research activities at school; fostering tolerance; using modern educational technologies.

The fundamental principle of educational work with migrant children in primary school is "from the native culture to the culture of the peoples of cohabitation, and then to the world culture" (from the near to the far, from the simple to the complex).

The main tasks of educational activities with migrant children in the process of primary school education are:

- Development of norms and skills of intercultural communication, education of respect for world cultures;
- Formation of communicative linguistic (usually bilingual) abilities, according to the requirements of life in a new society;
- Psychological support for immigrant children in the new socio-cultural environment;
- Explaining the child's rights and obligations;
- Preparation for the future professional life through the acquisition of general scientific and professional knowledge.

Acknowledgements

This paper has been supported by the Kazan Federal University Strategic Academic Leadership Program.

References

- Banks, J. (1996). Multicultural education: goals and dimensions. *New values of education: the cultural and multicultural environment of schools*, 4, 15-19.
- Berry, J. W. (1997). Immigration, acculturation, and adaptation. *Applied Psychology: An International Review*, 46(1), 5-34.
- Makarova E., & Birman, D. (2016). Minority students' psychological adjustment in the school context: an integrative review of qualitative research on acculturation. *Intercultural Education* 27(1), 1-21.
- Bondarevskaya, E. V. (1999). *Pedagogy: personality in humanistic theories and systems of education*. Rostov-on-Don: Uchitel.
- Cheung Judge, R. (2021). The best of both worlds': Lagos private schools as engaged strategists of transnational child-raising. *Journal of ethnic and migration studies*, 1-19.
- Chudnovsky, V. E. (2006). *The formation of personality and the problem of the meaning of life: Selected works*. Moscow: Publishing House of the Moscow Psychological and Social Institute.
- Dmitriev, G. D. (1999). *Multicultural education*. Moscow: Pedagogika.
- Guo, Q., Kim, Y. S. G., Liu, Y., Peng, Y., Sun, W. K., Wang, Y. J., & Yang, L. (2021). The effects of a summer reading program for migrant children in migrant schools: First-year results from a randomized experiment. *Asia pacific education review*, 22(1), 139-154.
- Herwartz-Emden, L., & Kuffner, D. (2006). Success at school and acculturation of primary school pupils with migration backgrounds. *Zeitschrift fur erziehungswissenschaft*, 9(2), 240-254.
- Jalalova, A. A. (2009). *Fundamentals of the development of multicultural competence of teachers*. (PhD thesis, Narva College of University of Tartu, Narva). Retrieved from: <https://docplayer.com/32707836-Osnovy-razvitiya-multikulturnoy-kompetentnosti-uchiteley.html>
- Kapustin, N. P. (2001). *Pedagogical technologies of the adaptive school*. Moscow: Academy.
- Katolik, G. A. (2016). Children of labor emigrants. Features of personal identity in adolescence. *Practical*

psychology and social work, 12, 31-33.

- Khukhlaev, O. E. (2005). Not like everyone else: psychological adaptation of migrant children from a foreign cultural environment in primary school (materials for training). *School psychologist, 18(352), 35-38.*
- Lemay, A. R. (2018). No Time for Church: School, Family and Filipino-Japanese Children's Acculturation. *Social science japan journal, 21(1), 9-25.*
- Levchenko, K. B., Trubavina, I. M., & Tsushko, I. I. (2008). *Socio-pedagogical and psychological work with the children of labor migrants.* Moscow: Nauka.
- Makaev, V. V., Malkova, Z. A., & Suprunova, L. L. (1999). Poly-cultural education - an actual problem of a modern school. *Pedagogy, 4, 3-10.*
- Molchanov, S. V. (2019). Features of the value orientations of the individual in adolescence and adolescence. *Psychological science and education, 3, 16-25.*
- Palatkina, G. V. (2001). Problems of multicultural educational space. *Pedagogical problems of the formation of subjectivity of a schoolboy, student, teacher in the system of continuous education: a collection of scientific and methodological works, 22-26.*
- Russell, D., & Fergusson, M. (2012). *Diagnostics of the level of social isolation of the individual.* Retrieved from: <https://psyera.ru/4976/metodika-dagnostiki-urovnya-subektivnogo-oshchushcheniya-odinochestva-d-rassela-i-m-fergyusona>
- Samoukina, N. (1997). *Practical psychology at school: lectures, counseling, trainings.* Moscow: INTOR.
- Sun, X. Y., Chui, E. W. T., Chen, J., & Fu, Y. Y. (2020). School Adaptation of Migrant Children in Shanghai: Accessing Educational Resources and Developing Relations. *Journal of child and family studies, 29(6), 1745-1756.*
- Switala, I., & Gurba, K. (2019). Children of emigrants and refugees in the polish educational system. 13th international technology, education and development conference. *Inted Proceedings, 3858-3865.*